

ON THE COMPETITION BETWEEN LAYERED SILICATES AND CELLULOSE NANO FIBRES DURING THE REINFORCEMENT OF BIODEGRADABLE POLYMER MATRIX

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SUMMARY

The expectation that the use of biocomposites in manufacturing will improve production speed and facilitate recycling has led to numerous approaches to the development of biodegradable material, which is increasingly being used in a wide range of manufacturing sectors. The nano dimension filler like cellulose and silicate layers have gained great importance due to the drastic alteration in properties at lower filler concentration. Cellulose nano-filler (CNF) and layered silicate were used as reinforcing agents for Poly (lactic acid) (PLA) in order to improve the thermal behaviour of composites which was not achievable by cellulose fiber alone. The silicate layers were having dominant influence on bulk properties than CNF and it is too early to use CNF based PLA matrixes for industrial applications. The aim of this work was to prepare and analyze composites made with CNF from grass and reinforced with a silicate layer to produce material with a cost that is comparable to existing biodegradable polymers

Keywords: Cellulose nano fibres, Silicate layers, Biocomposites.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, a renaissance in the use of nano filler from natural resources is taking place mainly to introduce eco-friendly character in resulting composites. After resolving incompatibility issues to a satisfactory degree by adequate modification of either host or filler, it is assumed that dispersion of natural fiber can be enhanced by a reduction in size by introducing nano size particle fillers for positive tailoring of different material properties. Nanosize (5–20 nm cross section with a length of 100 nm to several micrometers, depending on the source) rod-like cellulose crystallite particles [1] known as whiskers or nanofiber or nano-crystals can be extracted from laterally stabilized fibril bundles by removing the amorphous region of cellulose through controlled acid hydrolysis [2,3] and mechanical shearing. Additionally, the concentrations and orientations of the microfibrils and compatibilizer are critical to achieve the desired

mechanical properties. It has been observed that such type of highly crystalline cellulose has a unique and outstanding potential to increase the material properties of a composite, compared with those of unfilled polymer matrix or their micro-composite counterparts, at lower filler concentrations. PLA, starch, and polyolefin have been filled with cellulose nanowhiskers, but a greater dispersion is required [2]. The extrusion of cellulose nanowhiskey-based composites has major problems with uniform dispersion. If the suspension of cellulose nanowhiskers is allowed to mix with hot polymer, it generates a lot of vapor due to the fast removal of water, which again re-aggregates the cellulose crystals.

The mechanical properties of the resulting products seem to decrease after filling with nanofibers due to an extreme tendency to agglomeration. The composites, prepared by reinforcing with cellulose nano fiber exhibited remarkable improvement in many polymer matrixes [4]. These polymers are not designed for high temperature and low thermal stability with and poor dispersion is the main limitation for their use. It is well established that the stress transfer from polymer matrix to filler, decides the fate of a composite in terms of its different properties. The material properties of polymer composites are strongly dependent on the degree of intimate contact between the phases. It has been found that polymer filled with layered silicates often exhibit remarkable improvement of mechanical, thermal and physicochemical properties when compared with pure polymer even at very low filler concentration due to the nano-level interactions with polymer matrix [5]. These layered silicates have attracted great attention because of their cheap, easy availability and renewable nature and high aspect ratio which gives greater possibility of energy transfer from one phase to another. To ensure the best product, either a surfactant/modifier in clay, is adequate to offer sufficient excess enthalpy for the promotion of complete and homogenous dispersion of mineral filler in polymer or functionality in the host matrix is usually required. In the current research plan the modification of clay was attempted with cellulose fibers and aimed to establish the applicability of cellulose crystal based polymer matrix with comparative influence of both the fillers on final composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CNF was extracted with different treatments as per reported methods [6]. After physical cleaning and alkali soaking, the grass powder was treated for 1 h in 2% alkali solution. A mixture of acetate buffer and chlorite solution was used to bleach the grass until the colored substances were removed. The obtained suspension, after centrifugation and sonication, contained microfibrils and nanofibrils of ~10-60 nm width and 200-700 nm length, abbreviated as cellulose nano fiber. Cloisite Na⁺ (CN) (Southern Clay Products Inc) and CNF were filled in matrix (PLA after purification) at different concentrations. In a parallel attempt the CN modified with CNF (Figure 1, mixing CN and CNF in water and sonication at 10:90 ratios) was also used at similar load.

Attenuated Total Reflectance Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra of samples were recorded using the FT-IR 300E, Jasco spectrometer. Wide angle X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of samples was obtained by a Rigaku (Japan) diffractometer with Cu- K α radiation at 50 kV at the scan rate of 1° /minute. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was carried out by microscope from Topcon ((DS-130C), was used to study the

morphological changes at various stage of treatment. The samples of ~2.3 mm thickness were obtained in greased Petri dish and strips of specimen (width 5 mm and length between grips was 20 mm) were tested by Instron for measurement of comparative mechanical properties. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) (JEOL 2010 operating at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV) was applied to monitor the extent of modification / treatment on the shape and size of fiber. Thermo gravimetric Analysis (TGA) was conducted with a Seiko (Torrance, CA) model TG/DTA 32 thermal analysis system. The TGA scans were recorded at 10°C /min under nitrogen atmosphere from 50 to 500°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The micro/nano fibers were found embedded in the deep, surrounded by less ordered matrix which was removable after different treatment. The highly crystalline cellulose can be obtained by degradation of more assessable amorphous part through acid hydrolysis, which can form a stable suspension in aqueous medium. The bundles of fibers are constituted by small 'packets' of microfibers (Figure 2) those are not separated and arranged laterally one above each other with reduced thickness and could be separated by mechanical treatment of samples. To fuel the architectural conclusions made by SEM, TEM the samples were examined to study the functional groups changes, crystalline and thermal nature by FT-IR, XRD and TGA respectively. FT-IR analysis was performed to monitor carboxyl and hydroxyl region (1800 -1600 cm^{-1} for the C=O and 3600–3000 cm^{-1} for the OH vibrations) as these groups undergoes variations during conversion of macro to nano fiber [7]. In the present case a complication by the moisture absorption was removed by calibration with vacuum dried specimens.

The significant shift in 3500-3000 cm^{-1} toward higher frequencies in case of treated fiber must be due to the presence of more number of free exposed OH groups at the surface. Figure 3 illustrate the variations under carbonyl region where the peak at 1245 cm^{-1} assigned to methyl ester groups was vanished and establish the removal of hemicellulose. The vibration peak at 1257 cm^{-1} and 1510 cm^{-1} for benzene ring and -C-O stretching of lignin was disappeared due to the elimination of lignin from the treated fiber. The cellulose microfiber have the existence of both crystalline and amorphous regions with amorphous part of lower density in the nanocrystalline areas. Typical X-ray diffraction in Figure 3 for CNF and vacuum dried grass after passing through sieves and refluxing in ethanol and water solution, exhibited the changes of crystallinity as evidenced by the pattern and shape of diffraction peaks. In native grass two well defined peaks were present at $2\theta = 22.3$ and $2\theta = 34.5$ degrees with broader shoulder at $2\theta = 16.4$ degrees those can be correlated with (200) and (023) or (004) crystallographic planes respectively whereas broader shoulder at $2\theta = 16.4$ may be due to the (110) or ($\bar{1}\bar{1}0$). CNF presented two peaks at $2\theta = 15.5$ and $2\theta = 16.2$ degree for the (110) and ($\bar{1}\bar{1}0$) plane and sharp peaks reflect the presence of high crystallinity which is confirmation of presence of cellulose I.

TEM was employed to study the dispersion of CN which and it (5 % CN in PLA) shows roughly intercalated structure (Figure 4a) which proves the confinement of few polymer chains inside gallery space whereas at 7 % exhibited uneven distribution with

large and rough agglomerated factoids (Figure 4c). When CN, modified with CNF, used as filler a micrograph of better results could be captured in TEM presenting the higher dispersion at 5 % load (Figure 4 b). This shows that CN may help to reduce the agglomeration tendency of CNF most probably, by establishing the new bonding between CN and CNF charges, in solution casting of samples. The better dispersion of CN than CNF was indication of very high interlocking tendency of CNF due to distribution of highly polar hydroxyl groups over the large surface area. Although, better distribution of silicate layers may be evidenced by taking the TEM of very small specimens, still the same specimen may also contain the portion of agglomerated structures [8]. The order of reinforcing effect appeared as was CN > CN (modified with clay) > CNF after comparing tensile strength. The mechanical property analysis exhibited remarkable increase in modulus with filler load whereas, sacrifice of strength was observed at the same time. In all the samples the decrease in elongation at break was detected with concentration of filler. Similarly the temperature of 50% loss during Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) presented in Figure 5, showed improvement of thermal resistance in all the clay filled composites except CNF which may be attributed to the lower thermal stability of CNF due to more number of chains having free hydroxyl groups at end.

CONCLUSION

Reinforced composites composed of biodegradable polymer matrix with micro and nanofibers were prepared and their structure was analyzed. The approach was to improve the adhesion between matrices and cellulose crystals using a clay-filled cellulose fiber. After the removal of the amorphous region, the acid hydrolysis generated cellulose crystals those were separated into micro and nanofibres by mechanical treatment (sonication). The tentative indication of slight improvement in adhesion was observed for the composites of modified cellulose whiskers in comparison with samples prepared from unmodified filler during study of mechanical characteristics. It was qualitatively evident that the cellulose fiber modified clay may show comparatively better, mechanical properties than purified neat biodegradable polymer matrix. The agglomeration is the main challenge to use cellulose nano filler as reinforcer.

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Figure 1. Preparation of modified clay-polymer composites.

Figure 2. SEM of hydrolysed samples showing small packet like structures.

Figure 3. XRD and FT-IR spectra of treated samples where i and ii represent before and after treatment.

Figure 4. TEM micrographs of filler dispersion. a, b, c are 5, 5 and 7 % CN, modified clay in matrix.

Figure 5. TGA of different composites showing weight loss during analysis, Modi, represent the clay modified with cellulose.